

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

PLATE PROBLEMS FOR A CIRCULAR SEGMENT AND A HALF-PLANE WITH A SEGMENTAL NOTCH WITH MIXED BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The plane problem, for the circular segment and the half-plane with the segment recess, where at the boundary of the circular portion of the segment are given stresses, while on the other part of the contour given normal stresses and tangential displacements are considered. The problems are considered in bipolar system of coordinate using Fourier integrals and solutions are given in self contained.

Keywords: plane, segment, stress function, Fourier transform, bipolar coordinates.

Introduction. The problems are related to the problems of determining the stress-strain state in homogeneous and inhomogeneous elastic bodies, under mixed boundary conditions, which are of interest in theoretical and practical issues of the strength of various structures, which has become the subject of research by many authors, of which we note [1-6, 16,18-28,30].

In this paper, using bipolar coordinates and the Fourier integral apparatus, an exact solution is given to a plane problem of elasticity theory for a circular segment and a half-plane with a segmental notch under shifted boundary conditions.

Mathematical research method:

The problems are solved in a bipolar coordinate system. Relationship between bipolar coordinates (α, β) , and rectangular coordinates (x, y) are given by formulas [4-8,11-13,15,29]:

$$qx = sh\alpha, \quad qy = \sin \beta, \quad aq = ch\alpha - \cos \beta, \quad (1)$$

where a is the dimensional parameter.

The contour of a segment in bipolar coordinates is described by the coordinates $\beta = \beta_1$ and $\beta = 0$ (pic. 1) and a half-plane with a segmental notch $\beta = \beta_1$ и $\beta = -\pi$ (pic. 2).

Fig.1

Fig.2

Задача решается при помощи функций напряжений $\phi(\alpha, \beta)$, которая удовлетворяет бигармоническому уравнению:

$$\left[\frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \alpha^2 \partial \beta^2} + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \beta^4} - 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} + 1 \right] [q\phi(\alpha, \beta)] = 0 \quad (2)$$

Stresses and displacements in bipolar coordinates through stress functions $q\phi(\alpha, \beta)$ are given by the formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha\sigma_\alpha(\alpha, \beta) &= \left[(ch\alpha + \cos\beta) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial\beta^2} - sh\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha} + \sin\beta \frac{\partial}{\partial\beta} + ch\alpha \right] (q\phi) \\ \alpha\sigma_\beta(\alpha, \beta) &= \left[(ch\alpha + \cos\beta) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial\alpha^2} - sh\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha} + \sin\beta \frac{\partial}{\partial\beta} - \cos\beta \right] (q\phi) \\ \alpha\tau_{\alpha\beta}(\alpha, \beta) &= -(ch\alpha + \cos\beta) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial\alpha\partial\beta} (q\phi) \\ u(\alpha, \beta) &= \frac{1-2\nu}{2\mu} \left[\frac{\partial(q\phi)}{\partial\alpha} - \frac{sh\alpha}{ch\alpha + \cos\beta} (q\phi) \right] - \frac{1}{2\mu} \left[\frac{\partial(q\psi)}{\partial\beta} + \frac{\sin\beta}{ch\alpha + \cos\beta} (q\psi) \right] \\ v(\alpha, \beta) &= \frac{1-2\nu}{2\mu} \left[\frac{\partial(q\phi)}{\partial\beta} + \frac{\sin\beta}{ch\alpha + \cos\beta} (q\phi) \right] + \frac{1}{2\mu} \left[\frac{\partial(q\psi)}{\partial\alpha} - \frac{sh\alpha}{ch\alpha + \cos\beta} (q\psi) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where μ and ν elastic characteristics (μ – shear modulus, ν – Poisson's ratio) and the connection between $q\psi(\alpha, \beta)$, and $q\phi(\alpha, \beta)$ is given by the formula:

$$\frac{\partial^2(q\psi)}{\partial\alpha\partial\beta} = (1-\nu) \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial\alpha^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial\beta^2} - 1 \right] (q\phi) \quad (4)$$

Mathematical model of the problem:

Let the following boundary conditions be specified on the boundary of a circular segment:

normal and tangential stresses are specified on the circular part of the segment, and normal stresses and tangential displacements are specified on the other side of the segment, which are equivalent to the following conditions for the stress function:

$$\begin{aligned} [q\phi(\alpha, \beta)] \Big|_{\beta=\beta_1} &= \sigma_1(\alpha) ; \frac{\partial[q\phi(\alpha, \beta)]}{\partial\beta} \Big|_{\beta=\beta_1} = \tau_1(\alpha) \\ [q\phi(\alpha, \beta)] \Big|_{\beta=0} &= \sigma_0(\alpha) ; u(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_{\beta=0} = u_0(\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

for a half-plane with a segmental notch we have:

$$\begin{aligned} [q\phi(\alpha, \beta)] \Big|_{\beta=\beta_1} &= \sigma_1(\alpha) ; \frac{\partial[q\phi(\alpha, \beta)]}{\partial\beta} \Big|_{\beta=\beta_1} = \tau_1(\alpha) \\ [q\phi(\alpha, \beta)] \Big|_{\beta=-\pi} &= \sigma_0(\alpha) ; u(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_{\beta=-\pi} = u_0(\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

It is assumed that $\sigma_1(\alpha)$, $\tau_1(\alpha)$, $\sigma_0(\alpha)$ и $u_0(\alpha)$ satisfy the conditions of expansion in the Fourier integral.

$$q\phi(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t, \beta) \exp(-it\alpha) dt \quad (7)$$

Stress function $\phi(\alpha, \beta)$ we are looking for it in the form of a Fourier integral.

where for a circular segment

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, \beta) &= A(t)cht(\beta_1 - \beta) \cos\beta + B(t)cht\beta \cos(\beta_1 - \beta) + \\ &+ c(t)sht(\beta_1 - \beta) \sin\beta + D(t)sht\beta(\beta_1 - \beta) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

for a half-plane with a segmental recess

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, \beta) &= -A(t)cht(\beta_1 - \beta) \cos\beta + B(t)cht(\pi + \beta) \cos(\beta_1 - \beta) - \\ &- c(t)sht(\beta_1 - \beta) \sin\beta + D(t)sht(\pi + \beta) \sin(\beta_1 - \beta) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_1(t)A(t) &= 2\bar{\sigma}_0(t)cht\beta_1 - 2\bar{\sigma}_1(t)\cos\beta_1 \\
 \Delta_1(t)B(t) &= 2\bar{\sigma}_1(t)cht\beta_1 - 2\bar{\sigma}_0(t)\cos\beta_1 \\
 \Delta_2(t)C(t) &= 2\bar{u}_0(t)sht\beta_1 + 2\bar{\tau}_1(t)\cos\beta_1 + A(t)(tsh2t\beta_1 + \sin 2\beta_1) \\
 \Delta_2(t)D(t) &= -2t\bar{u}_0(t)sht\beta_1 - 2\bar{\tau}_1(t)cht\beta_1 - 2(t^2 + 1)A(t)cht\beta_1 \sin\beta_1 + t\Delta_2(t)B(t)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{10}$$

Substituting (7) into (5) and (6) taking into account (3) and (4) for the circular segment problem we obtain the following values for the unknown integration quantities $A(t), B(t), C(t), D(t)$:

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_1(t) &= ch2t\beta_1 - \cos 2\beta_1, \quad \Delta_2(t) = sh2t\beta_1 - \sin\beta \sin 2\beta_1 \\
 \bar{\sigma}_1(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sigma_1(\alpha) \exp(i\alpha t) d\alpha, \quad \bar{\tau}_1(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tau_1(\alpha) \exp(i\alpha t) d\alpha \\
 \bar{\sigma}_0(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sigma_0(\alpha) \exp(i\alpha t) d\alpha \\
 \bar{u}_0(t) &= -\frac{1-2\nu}{2(1-\nu)} t\bar{\sigma}_0(t) + \frac{i}{2(1-\nu)\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [(1-2\nu)]th\frac{\alpha}{2} \sigma_0(\alpha) + 2\mu u_0(\alpha) \exp(i\alpha t) d\alpha
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

For the problem of a half-plane with a segmental notch, we obtain the value (10) and (11), only instead of β_1 need to be substituted $\pi + \beta_1$ and $cth\frac{\alpha}{2}$. The solution of problems on the extension of an infinite plane weakened by a dimpled hole was given [20-26].

Special cases.

As a parameter, we will consider a circular segment subject to sections of the lateral surface $|\alpha| < \alpha_0$ uniform normal distribution of intensity q , there is no tangential stress and on the other side of the circular segment or half-plane there is no tangential stress;

$$\sigma_\beta(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_{\beta = \beta_1} = \begin{cases} -q, & |\alpha| < \alpha_0 \\ 0, & |\alpha| > \alpha_0 \end{cases}, \quad \tau_{\alpha, \beta}(\alpha, \beta) \Big|_{\beta = \beta_1} = 0$$

It is necessary to create boundary conditions for the given contour values $\sigma_1(\alpha), \tau_1(\alpha), \sigma_0(\alpha)$ and $u_0(\alpha)$. After some calculations we find:

$$\sigma_1(\alpha) = \begin{cases} qa \frac{1 - \exp(-\alpha_0)ch\alpha}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1} + \frac{aq}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1} (sh\alpha_0 \cos\beta_1 - \sin^2\beta_1) & |\alpha| < \alpha_0 \\ \frac{qash\alpha_0 \cdot \exp(-\alpha)}{sh\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1} + \frac{aq}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1} (sh\alpha_0 \cos\beta_1 - \sin^2\beta_1) & |\alpha| > \alpha_0 \end{cases}
 \tag{13}$$

$$\tau_1(\alpha) = -\frac{qa}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1} (\sin\beta_1 \cos\beta_1 + sh\alpha_0 \sin\beta_1)$$

$$\sigma_0(\alpha) = \frac{qash\alpha_0}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1}, \quad u_0(\alpha) = 0$$

For the problem of a half-plane with a segmental notch

$$\sigma_0(\alpha) = -\frac{qash\alpha_0}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1}
 \tag{14}$$

Due to the fact that a constant value cannot be expanded by the Fourier integral the required stress functions are represented by the coordinate $\phi(\alpha, \beta)$ as a sum of two biharmonic functions $\phi_1(\alpha, \beta)$ и $\phi_2(\alpha, \beta)$

$$\phi(\alpha, \beta) = \phi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \phi_2(\alpha, \beta)
 \tag{15}$$

Inharmonic functions $\phi_1(\alpha, \beta)$ can be represented in the following form

$$q\phi_2(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{qa}{ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1} (sh\alpha_0 \cos\beta - \sin\beta \sin\beta_1)
 \tag{16}$$

Unknown function $\phi_1(\alpha, \beta)$ we will represent it in the form of an integral as in the formula (7). After satisfying the boundary conditions (13) for the value of the unknowns of integration for a circular segment we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_1(t)A(t) &= -2\sigma(t)\cos\beta_1, \quad \Delta_1(t)B(t) = 2\bar{\sigma}(t)\operatorname{cht}(\pi + \beta_1) \\ \Delta_1(t)\Delta_2(t)C(t) &= -2\sigma(t)\cos\beta_1[tsh2t\beta_1 + \sin 2\beta_1] - 2\bar{u}(t)\Delta_1(t)\operatorname{sht}(\pi + \beta_1) \\ \Delta_1(t)\Delta_2(t)D(t) &= 2\bar{\sigma}(t)\operatorname{cht}(\pi + \beta_1)[tsh2t(\pi + \beta_1) + \sin 2\beta_1] + 2\bar{u}(t)\Delta_1(t)\sin\beta_1\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

were:

$$\bar{\sigma}(t) = \frac{2qa \sin t\alpha_0}{t(t^2+1)(ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1)\sqrt{2\pi}}; \quad \bar{u}(t) = \frac{\pi qash\alpha_0}{\sqrt{2\pi}(ch\alpha_0 + \cos\beta_1)} \frac{1-2\nu}{1-\nu} \frac{1}{\operatorname{sht}\pi} \quad (18)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}(t) = \frac{P}{(t^2+1)\sqrt{2\pi}}; \quad \bar{u}(t) = \frac{\pi P}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1-2\nu}{1-\nu} \frac{1}{\operatorname{sht}\pi} \quad (19)$$

For a half-plane with a segmental recess in (17) together β_1 need to be substituted $\pi + \beta_1$, and (18) remains unchanged. In case at point α_0 , $\beta = \beta_1$ concentrated force applied P , then by passing to the limit we obtain.

Let us calculate the values of shear stresses in a particular case at $\beta_1 = \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\beta_1 = \pi$ in the first case and

$\beta_1 = -\frac{\pi}{2}$, $\beta_1 = 0$ и $\beta_1 = \pi$ in the second case, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{\alpha,\beta}(\alpha,0) \Big|_{\beta_1 = \frac{\pi}{2}} &= \frac{Pch^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\pi a} \left[\frac{1-2\nu}{4(1-\nu)} \frac{sh\alpha - \alpha ch\alpha}{sh^2\alpha} + \frac{1-2\nu}{16(1-\nu)} \frac{\alpha(2+ch\alpha) - 3sh\alpha}{sh^4 \frac{\alpha}{2}} + \frac{sh\alpha}{ch^2\alpha} \right] \\ \tau_{\alpha,\beta}(t,0) \Big|_{\beta_1 = \pi} &= -\frac{P(1-2\nu)}{16a(1-\nu)} sh \frac{\alpha}{2} \\ \tau_{\alpha,\beta}(\alpha_1, -\pi) \Big|_{\beta_1 = -\frac{\pi}{2}} &= -\frac{Psh^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{\pi a} \left[\frac{t-2\nu}{4(1-\nu)} \frac{sh\alpha - \alpha ch\alpha}{sh^2\alpha} + \frac{1-2\nu}{16(1-\nu)} \frac{\alpha(2+ch\alpha) - 3sh\alpha}{sh^4 \frac{\alpha}{2}} - \frac{sh\alpha}{ch^2\alpha} \right] \\ \tau_{\alpha,\beta}(\alpha_1, -\pi) \Big|_{\beta_1 = 0} &= \frac{P}{16a} th^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} sh \frac{\alpha}{2} \\ \tau_{\alpha,\beta}(\alpha_1, -\pi) \Big|_{\beta_1 = \pi} &= -\frac{P}{8a} \frac{1-2\nu}{1-\nu} \frac{sh^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{ch^2 \frac{\alpha}{4}} \left[sh \frac{\alpha}{4} ch \frac{\alpha}{2} - 2ch \frac{\alpha}{4} sh \frac{\alpha}{2} \right]\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

Conclusion:

We consider plane problems for a circular segment of a half-plane with a segmental notch under mixed boundary conditions. Using the stress function and Fourier integrals in the bipolar coordinate system. The problem is solved in a closed manner. In a particular case, if at a point $\alpha = 0$, $\beta = \beta_1$ a concentrated force of magnitude

is applied P the values of shear stresses in the first case were calculated $\beta_1 = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\beta = \pi$ case and

$\beta_1 = -\frac{\pi}{2}$, $\beta_1 = 0$ and $\beta_1 = \pi$ in the second case.

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